

WAYS TO IMPROVE MARKETING ACTIVITIES AT "TRANSAVTOTREYD" LLC

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Abstract. In this article, the company will determine the market opportunities, analyze the activities of competitors, their strengths and weaknesses, the importance of marketing activity in the development of market relations, free competition and ensuring the well-being of the population was considered.

Keywords: company, activity, market, analysis, competition, service, attitude.

The organization of marketing activities in the field of enterprises and organizations is based, first of all, on the nature, content and direction of research in the field of marketing. The importance of marketing research in the organization, management, planning and control of gross marketing activities is manifested as one of the main features of modern marketing theory.

The main activity of the company is the provision of transport services to organizations and individuals who use transport services. Payment for the rendered services is made on the basis of cash and non-cash settlement.

The organization offers a large amount of transport from Gazelle to Eurofura, as well as several dump trucks, cranes and timber trucks. This allows the company to find the right transport when receiving an order from the carrier and provide it to the customer on time.

The target audience of an organization focused on managing marketing activities is production organizations, organizations that regularly ship goods from warehouses, construction sites, as well as people who rent small cars for moving, etc.

To analyze the company's work, it is necessary to know the internal and external factors that affect the company's performance. The organization does not have a secure state, it depends on the external and internal environment. For this, we will analyze Swoti step by step.

Table 1

"TransautotradeThe number of employees in LLC in 2022

N o		Unit of measure	2022 year			
			1 quarter	2 quarte rs	3 quarters	4 quarters
1	Total number of employees	person	6745	7014	7195	7657
2	The number of workers in production	person	5147	6424	5547	5258
3	Including workers who create products	person	1365	1542	1456	1567

4	The number of employees not related to production	person	200	452	452	450
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External environmental factors are very important for managing the organization. This leads to rapid changes in the economic conditions of the enterprises. The market economy must take into account changes in the external environment, because the organization as an open system depends on the supply of resources, energy, personnel and consumers to the outside world. Since the survival of the organization depends on the management, they identify the important factors of the environment and suggest appropriate ways to respond to external influences.

The analysis of the internal factors of the organization allows to evaluate and forecast the development of the components of the internal environment of the organization. SWOT analyzes help to determine the reasons for the company's effective or ineffective performance in the market, it is a brief analysis of marketing data, in which the organization is determined by the development of its business and, ultimately, the distribution of resources by segment. The results of the analysis are the development of a marketing strategy or hypothesis for future development.

Table 2

STEP-analysis of "Transavtotrade" LLC»

A group of factors	Factor	Demonstration of the factor	The possible reaction of the organization
Social	Unemployment rate	Cheap labor. State reduction.	Formation of a rational personnel structure.
	Migration	Migration of skilled personnel from the regions.	1. Increasing the reputation of the company. 2. Improvement of working conditions.
	Consumer perception and attitude	Organizations using cargo transportation services in Shayhontokhur, Elektrostal (Shayhontokhur district).	1. Increasing the company's rating in the market of transport services. 2. Evaluation and analysis of competitors. 3. Publications about "Transavtotreyd" in mass media. 4. Differentiation of transport. 5. To create a more comfortable environment for the consumer than competitors. 6. High-quality and fast execution of orders.
Technological	New technologies in the field of ecology	Development of new technologies designed to take environmental factors into account.	Transition to gasoline engine cars.

	Development of competitive technologies	Rapid information processing system, well-organized communication system.	1. Accurate fulfillment of shipping orders. 2. Development of special navigation programs for cargo tracking.
	NEW features	The emergence of new technologies for storing cargo, as well as downloading and unloading it.	1. Encourage use, convenient use. 2. Equipping transport with cooling and refrigeration equipment for transporting frozen food. 3. Warehouse equipment for all types of goods.
Economical	Inflation	8.5%	Increase in the price of services.
	Economic situation	Unfavorable economic environment for businesses. Predominance of expenses over income.	1. Optimization of transport costs. 2. To maintain a position in the market of transport services, to establish permanent relationships with customers. 3. Creating a system of flexible calculation and discounts.
Political	Tax decisions of the government	Tax norms.	Transition from simplified taxation system to VAT.
	Ecological requirements	Consideration of environmental factors.	Reducing harmful emissions into the atmosphere.

From these tables there are threats of "Transavtotreyd" LLC, strengths and weaknesses of the organization, as well as opportunities that the company leader can use and implement all ideas in business. Naturally, in order to implement any idea, the company must enter the market with a new type of product and not tolerate defeat.

Table 3

SWOT-analysis of "Transavtotrade" LLC:

Strengths	Weaknesses
1. Flexible price system. 2. The ability to quickly process the order and provide the necessary transportation. 3. Highly qualified staff. 4. Availability of a warm storage room. 5. Great selection of transport.	1. Disadvantages of general management. 2. Lack of own car park. 3. Small customer base. 4. There is not enough money for quality advertising. 5. Low performance in the transport services market.
Opportunities	Threats

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Opening branches of the company in other cities of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2. Establishing a system of transportation of collective cargoes. 3. Establishing connections with construction facilities (use of cranes and dump trucks). 4. Create your own car fleet. 5. Provision of forwarding services. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Unfavorable financial and economic situation. Decrease in income. 2. Decrease in efficiency of transport customers. 3. High competition of developed companies. 4. Adverse weather conditions.
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When the transport company "Transavtotreyd" LLC started its activity, it did not have such a budget that would allow it to compete with large companies in the mass media, but it was necessary to publicize its services.

One of the main goals of marketing research is to determine the company's market opportunities. The size of the market, its growth potential and possible profit should be correctly estimated and estimated. Sales forecasts are used by the finance department to raise working capital or investment, the production department to determine capacity and planned performance, the supply department to make purchases to meet needs, and the human resources department. - to hire the necessary workforce. After all, if the forecast is far from reality, the company spends money on building excess reserves and production capacity, or cannot meet market needs, and loses income.

Table 4

Total salary fund in 2022

No		Unit of measure	2022 year				Total
			1 quarter	2 quarters	3 quarters	4 quarters	
1	Total number of employees	m. soum	1853149 4	1873741 7	1997284 5	1906669 86	7630878 60
2	The number of workers in production	m. soum	1422620 2	1430108 3	1538675 6	1458178 86	5842495 90
3	Including workers who create products	m. soum	3743735	3893498	4062452	3942421 6	1562003 90
4	The number of employees not related to production	m. soum	561569	542847	561756	5436284	2206588 0

The total amount of salary is 763087860 thousand soums. In the next table, we see the average salary estimate. Increasing the monthly salaries of every employee is included among the strategic tasks of the enterprise. This means raising the wages of each employee in a competitive society and, as a result, increasing the size and breadth of the employees' consumption basket.

The management of the current activity of "Transavtotreyd" company is carried out by the director of the company - the executive body.

The organizational structure of marketing activities in the enterprise is defined as the design of the organization in which marketing management is carried out, that is, a set of departments and units that include employees engaged in marketing activities.

Analyzing the activities of competitors shows their strengths and weaknesses, allowing to determine which strategies are most effective. In addition, the very question of who can be considered competitors in the field can provide a lot of useful information. It is important to analyze the competitor:

- * opponent's goals and strategy;
- * opponent's weaknesses;
- * competitor's available resources;
- * leadership, corporate culture and management.

Entering the transport services market, "Transavtotreyd" LLC encountered a number of competitors providing similar services. The main and strongest competitor is "POGAT" LLC.

The main activity of the company is cargo transportation. Various brands, modifications of the traffic structure allow to provide internal and intercity and international transport (CIS countries, Baltic states). Kamaz, maz, gaz-3307 cars, cars with special bodies (including for transporting bakery products in trays), tentovannymi semi-trailer tractors from 62 to 82 cubic meters, as well as transportation of containers with a carrying capacity of 20 and 40 tons There are cars designed for. In addition to the main activity, auto renewal provides the following services:

- repair and maintenance of cars, sanitary treatment of the body;
- training of drivers and specialists in various programs on traffic safety and transportation of dangerous goods;
- rental of production and office space;
- placement of vehicles in an open protected parking lot;
- grinding of crankshafts, grinding of brake drums, repair of cylinder blocks, repair and adjustment of fuel equipment of gas, ZIL, Kamaz, YAMZ engines.

From this description of the company, it is clear that "POGAT" has a strong position in the field of transport services and is very well known among consumers.

Summarizing the practical part of the research, "Transavtotreyd" LLC has a number of advantages and disadvantages. Disadvantages hinder its development and significantly limit the organization's capabilities, which is mainly due to the suppression of the company by its competitors. The advantages of "Transavtotreyd" are a well-organized working mechanism, a variety of cargo transportation, a flexible system of prices for services, and a convenient location.

External and internal factors affecting the organization's activities are considered in STEP and SWOT analysis tables. The management of the company should approach each problem individually and get out of difficult situations in a logical way.

The company's goals do not always lead to the expected results. In such cases, the management should improve the work of its organization by analyzing all the factors related to its activity. For example, consider the transport enterprise "Transavtotreyd" LLC. In order to solve the problem of providing highly qualified personnel in the personnel management system at "Transavtotreyd" LLC, a vocational training center should be established. To do this, you will need to find a suitable room, equip it, hire an educational manager. Staff training costs include: renting classroom buildings, purchasing furniture, purchasing computers and other tools for the educational process, as well as

The program of the training center is conducted in the form of seminars, trainings, master classes and video courses. It is recommended to train once or twice on weekends. This ensures the

delay of employees from the main work and spends free time on free training, most employees agree.

Measures for the creation of a corporate education system and the development of employees - the development and implementation of measures - the introduction of a new management position for employees to increase labor productivity, reduce the number of redundant workers, increase the culture of employee management, improve the professional skills of employees, as well as work discipline allows to increase.

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